

Major citations to the reviews on vitamin C and the common cold by Chalmers (1975) and by Dykes and Meier (1975).

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Linus Pauling's 1970 book *Vitamin C and the Common Cold* generated widespread interest in vitamin C,² and as a consequence numerous controlled trials were published in the 1970s (Figure). However, interest in the topic declined sharply after the mid-1970s (Figure). This rapid loss of interest can be attributed largely to the reviews by Chalmers (1975) and Dykes and Meier (1975), as well as to the randomized trial by Karlowski, Chalmers, et al. (1975).³

This document lists influential publications that cited the reviews by Chalmers (1975) or Dykes and Meier (1975) as evidence that vitamin C is ineffective against the common cold. The purpose of this compilation is to illustrate the substantial influence these two reviews.

Figure. The numbers of participants over time in randomized trials for which ≥ 1 g/d of vitamin C was administered. The numbers of participants in studies published over two consecutive years are combined and plotted for the first of the two years. This figure is from Hemilä and Chalker (2022).³

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

2 Linus Pauling and vitamin C, and biographies of Linus Pauling.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20374065>

3 Hemilä H, Chalker E. Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: examples from trials of vitamin C for infections. *Life (Basel)*. 2022 Jan 3;12(1):62.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>

In 1970, Linus Pauling published *Vitamin C and the Common Cold*, in which he argued that vitamin C is beneficial against the common cold.² In 1971, he followed this with a meta-analysis of four placebo-controlled trials, concluding that it was highly unlikely that the reported benefits in the vitamin C groups could be explained by chance alone ($P < 0.000022$).⁴

Pauling's work stimulated a series of new randomized trials on vitamin C and the common cold. Before the 1970s, only one trial had examined the regular use of vitamin C doses of ≥ 1 g/day throughout the study (Ritzel 1961). Within a decade of Pauling's book, however, over a dozen new trials using similarly high doses were published.

Interest in vitamin C and the common cold declined sharply in the late-1970s. This decline was driven largely by the publication of two negative reviews in wide-circulation journals (Chalmers 1975; Dykes & Meier 1975), as well as by a particularly influential randomized placebo-controlled trial conducted at the National Institutes of Health and published in *JAMA*, which concluded that the apparent benefits of vitamin C could be explained entirely by the placebo effect (Karlowski et al. 1975).

Flaws in these three 1975 reports have been described previously, and they are not discussed in this document.^{3,5} An earlier version of the list was published as Table 3 in Hemilä and Chalker (2022).³

The reviews:

Chalmers TC (1975) Effects of ascorbic acid on the common cold: An evaluation of the evidence.

Am J Med 58:532-6. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1092164>

Dykes MHM, Meier P (1975) Ascorbic acid and the common cold: Evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. *JAMA* 231:1073-9. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1089817>

The Karlowski trial:

Karlowski TR, Chalmers TC, Frenkel LD, Kapikian AZ, Lewis TL, Lynch JM (1975)

Ascorbic acid for the common cold: a prophylactic and therapeutic trial.

JAMA 231:1038-42. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/163386>

4 Pauling L. The significance of the evidence about ascorbic acid and the common cold. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 1971
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4941984>

5 Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C: A list of critiques by Harri Hemilä.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426>
Hemilä H. Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? Thesis 2006 p.21-27,36-38,42-45,59-60,63-66.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395595>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>
Hemilä H, Herman ZS. Vitamin C and the common cold: a retrospective analysis of Chalmers' review. *J Am Coll Nutr*. 1995 Apr;14(2):116-23.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/7790685>
<https://zenodo.org/records/18376955>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/42358>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/15407891>
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.1995.10718483>
Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms: problems with inaccurate reviews. *Nutrition*. 1996 Nov-Dec;12(11-12):804-9.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8974108>
<https://zenodo.org/records/18377079>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10250/7979>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/14233989>
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007\(96\)00223-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007(96)00223-7)

Major citations to the reviews by Chalmers (1975) and by Dykes and Meier (1975).

Source [Ref.]	Statement
TIME (1975) [1]	Ever since Linus Pauling proposed in 1970 that large doses of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) would prevent or cure the common cold, sales of the vitamin have soared, despite the widely expressed doubts of other researchers. Three reports now cast a further shadow on Pauling's theory. In one of two studies published in the A.M.A. Journal ... In the second Journal [Dykes and Meier 1975] report, researchers at the University of Chicago say that after a review of various studies of vitamin C conducted from 1939 to 1973, there is little convincing evidence of the vitamin's effectiveness in preventing or curing colds. Moreover, they find evidence that large daily doses may even be medically harmful, producing diarrhea or kidney stones.
New York Times (1975) [2]	Two reports published today in the Journal of the American Medical Association conclude that Vitamin C shows little merit in treatment of the common cold... The other [Dykes and Meier 1975] report was a review of many previous studies from 1938 to the present. In this report the authors concluded that use of the vitamin for the common cold "cannot be advocated on the basis of the evidence currently available."
American Medical Association (1987) [4]	One of the most widely misused vitamins is ascorbic acid. There is no reliable evidence that large doses of ascorbic acid prevent colds or shorten their duration [Chalmers 1975]
Recommended Dietary Allowances, 9th ed (1980) [5]	several reviewers (Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975) believe that these benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population
Recommended Dietary Allowances, 10th ed (1989) [6]	Several reviewers (Chalmers, 1975; Dykes and Meier, 1975) have concluded that any benefits of large doses of ascorbic acid for these conditions are too small to justify recommending routine intake of large amounts by the entire population
Dietary Reference Intakes for Vitamin C, Vitamin E, Selenium and Carotenoids (2000) [7]	Reviews of numerous studies generally conclude that vitamin C megadoses have no significant effect on incidence of the common cold, but do provide a moderate benefit in terms of the duration and severity of episodes in some groups (Chalmers, 1975) ...
Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases (1979,1985, 1990,1995) [8-10]	Until truly effective and specific treatment becomes available, there will continue to be fads in the use of unproven remedies. The ingestion of large doses of vitamin C has been widely used as a preventive or therapeutic measure for colds. However, a careful analysis of the studies has indicated that a placebo effect could not be ruled out [Chalmers 1975]
Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases (2015) [11]	Nonpharmacologic interventions touted as effective prophylaxis for the common cold include zinc; vitamins C, D, and E; Echinacea; ginseng; exercise; and hand hygiene. Unfortunately, when these interventions have been subjected to rigorous evaluation, evidence for effectiveness has not been found. [Dykes and Meier, 1975]
Infectious Diseases: A Modern Treatise of Infectious Processes (1989) [12]	There is no proof of any curative value from the many proprietary remedies containing vitamins (including vitamin C) ... in the treatment of the common cold [Chalmers 1975]
Human Nutrition and Dietetics,	... claiming that large daily doses of vitamin C reduced the likelihood of

9th ed (1993) [13]	contracting the common cold. The popularity of this concept prompted at least 14 clinical trials, which failed to show an effect of vitamin C (Chalmers 1975)
Human Nutrition and Dietetics, 10th ed (2000) [14]	Chalmers (1975) carried out a similar analysis of 14 clinical trials and reported that severity of symptoms was significantly worse in patients who received the placebo. Unfortunately, many volunteers correctly guessed their treatment and when this was taken into account, differences in both the number and severity of colds were minor and insignificant
Nutrition, Concepts and Controversies, 2nd ed (1982), 6th ed (1994) [15,16]	... in 1975 a physician [Chalmers] reviewed many of them. He found that, statistically, takers of vitamin C did indeed suffer fewer and milder colds than takers of placebos. The difference averaged ... one tenth of one day per cold in favor of the vitamin C-takers
Modern Nutrition in Health and Disease, 8th ed (1994) [17]	The use of megadoses of vitamin C to prevent the common upper respiratory diseases remains an unproven claim. Fourteen studies have been reviewed of which eight were considered acceptable [Chalmers 1975]. Only minor and insignificant effects were noted in terms of the prophylactic benefit of administering megadoses of vitamin C
BMJ (1976) [18]	... Both have been criticised on the grounds of their difficulties in maintaining “blind conditions,” in reporting symptoms, and in statistical analysis. [Dykes and Meier (1975)] A more recent American study of adult employees of the National Institutes of Health reported in 1975 found no significant prophylactic or therapeutic benefit from ascorbic acid. [Karlowski (1975)]
Lancet (1979) [19]	Vitamin C, contrary to the suggestion of Pauling, does not seem to decrease the incidence of colds and winter illness [Chalmers (1975)]
New England Journal of Medicine (1980) [20]	Other compounds, such as... vitamin C,... have been extensively studied in vitro and in vivo but have not been proved safe and effective antiviral agents [Chalmers (1975) and Dykes and Meier (1975)]
Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy (1988) [21]	One clinical trial of ascorbic acid showed that the apparent benefit in the vitamin C recipients was accounted for by volunteers who had tasted the contents of their capsules and correctly identified the treatment. Reanalysis with omission of these subjects found no evidence of a treatment benefit [Chalmers (1975)]
Pediatric infectious disease journal (1988) [22]	Preliminary studies suggesting efficacy were flawed by inadequate experimental design [Chalmers (1975)]
New England Journal of Medicine (1990) [23]	That an agent is inexpensive, easy to administer, free of appreciable risk at the recommended dose, and hypothetically beneficial does not justify its widespread use. These criteria fit virtually every placebo. Vitamin C fulfilled them for treatment of the common cold but was largely ineffective in controlled studies [Chalmers (1975)]
PloS Medicine (2010) [24]	Box 1. Early Systematic Reviews of the Effects of Health Care Interventions:... Chalmers TC (1975) Effects of ascorbic acid on the common cold. An evaluation of the evidence. Am J Med 58: 532-536.
Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine (2016) [25]	[Chalmers (1975)] brought together 14 trials of ascorbic acid for the common cold and combined the results from eight of them... All differences in severity and duration were eliminated by analyzing only the data from those who did not know which drug they were taking

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